

Derivation of thesauri in archaeological conservation

Synergistic collaboration between domain experts and the use of semantic and NLP technologies with a FAIR and open publication

Abstract

Digital technologies are increasingly central in preserving archaeological cultural heritage, with structured data management being a key factor. However, the diversity of existing solutions, lacking standardised approaches, hampers interdisciplinary collaboration. The NFDI4Objects consortium, particularly the "Protecting" task area, aims to harmonise this fragmented data landscape to enhance the accessibility and exchange of conservation data. This project demonstrates the development of semantically networked, machine-readable thesauri using the Leibniz Centre for Archaeology (LEIZA) conservation terminology as a case study. The process begins with systematically cataloguing existing terms from archival documents and the daily language used by conservators, supplemented by machine processing through Natural Language Processing (NLP). The methodology combines human expertise with semantic modelling techniques, transforming the terminology into the RDF schema according to SKOS standards. The results include initial vocabulary lists, visual representations of hierarchical structures, and data integration into Linked Open Data (LOD) environments. This approach facilitates more precise communication across disciplines, enables the semantic linking of diverse data sources, and generates new knowledge by connecting existing information. The approach addresses challenges such as terminological uncertainties and ambiguities, establishing a foundation for future innovations in managing cultural heritage data. By combining human expertise with AI-driven technologies, this study contributes to the sustainable and standardised documentation of archaeological conservation processes.

Introduction

The advent of digitisation has precipitated a transformation in numerous scientific and cultural disciplines, thereby engendering novel prospects in conservation science. The implementation of comprehensive digital documentation facilitates the accurate documentation of the present state of objects, the systematic analysis of damage patterns and alterations in condition over time, and the long-term recording of conservation interventions and materials employed. Interventions that modify an object's physical structure or appearance constitute a new event in its history, which, like the object itself, should be preserved for future generations as it provides valuable insights into the object's history and treatment (Beck, 2013).

An object's biography does not end with its deposition in the ground or excavation; it is continuously enriched through handling, conservation, and research activities. Early records of such information, aimed at ensuring traceability of an object's ongoing biography and the impacts of past interventions, were made using handwritten index cards, process sheets, or notes. Today, digitisation offers more

sustainable and efficient ways to capture this data and make it accessible across institutional and disciplinary boundaries. These advances promote the scholarly study of cultural heritage and interdisciplinary collaboration between institutions and fields, extending the preservation of cultural heritage beyond traditional approaches.

Despite these advancements, the professional community faces significant challenges in managing and utilising the growing volume of data. A key issue is the lack of standardisation and the fragmentation of the digital data landscape. Many institutions rely on isolated systems and proprietary solutions that are neither interoperable nor conducive to effective knowledge exchange between institutions and disciplines. Much of the conservation-specific data exists as textual reports, photographs, drawings, and mappings that lack unified formats and metadata. Additionally, divergent terminologies and heterogeneous documentation practices further hinder collaboration and the development of a shared understanding of documented objects and interventions. Moreover, technical and organisational barriers, such as outdated software and a shortage of specialised IT professionals, threaten the long-term accessibility and usability of digital conservation data. Without systematic knowledge sharing, conservation professionals often have to address challenges independently, missing the opportunity to learn from the experiences of others. This can result in treating similar damages on objects with disparate and sometimes ineffective methods. At the same time, valuable expertise in specific conservation techniques, materials, or tools is lost if individual practitioners do not share their insights widely.

Establishing common standards, interoperable infrastructures, and the systematic use of controlled vocabularies foster a global, coherent knowledge network. This network allows for the accurate documentation and sharing of experiences, methods, and findings. Such approaches significantly enhance clarity and consistency in scientific communication within conservation and provide the foundation for innovative, data-driven methodologies such as big data analytics and machine learning. Ultimately, these efforts contribute substantially to the preservation of our cultural heritage

Applying RDM and the FAIR principles in Conservation Science

The consortium *NFDI4Objects* (Thiery et al., 2023; Bibby et al., 2023) aims to harmonise the fragmented data landscape concerning human legacies from cultural history, unlocking new potential for knowledge generation and interdisciplinary linking. Within the consortium, *Task Area 4, "Protecting"* (Himmelmann et al., 2024; Fella, Mempel-Länger, and Witt, 2024) focuses on managing and protecting cultural heritage, improving the accessibility and exchange of conservation data and facilitating interdisciplinary research using data-driven methodologies. Achieving these goals requires addressing barriers such as using disparate specialised terminologies. Different terms can describe the same objects or conservation methods even within individual communities of practice, complicating clear communication and understanding of defined entities. This challenge intensifies across disciplinary boundaries. Controlled vocabularies offer a solution by enabling uniform and precise communication, enhancing clarity and consistency in scientific collaboration (Harpring, 2010). Many

conservation institutions already possess internal terminologies, such as glossaries or wordlists, encompassing terms for damage patterns, interventions, or manufacturing techniques. However, these resources are often intended for internal use only, lack standardised frameworks, and are thus limited in their interoperability. *Task Area 4* in *NFDI4Objects* aims to systematically curate these valuable resources (Thiery et al., 2025). Developing a universal vocabulary is impractical due to the diversity of the disciplines and institutions involved. Instead, the focus is on semantic modelling and linking, creating an interconnected network of meanings from individual specialised vocabularies.

For this approach to succeed, datasets must adhere to and implement the *FAIR principles* — *Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable* (Wilkinson et al., 2016) — by Semantic Web technologies and formalisms such as *Linked Open Data (LOD)* (Berners-Lee, 2006). LOD combines structured open data based on semantic web technologies, e.g. *Resource Description Framework (RDF)* (Schreiber and Raimond, 2014), to link knowledge in a contextualised and machine-readable way. This digital methodology and standardised technology ensure that data is accessible but also interoperable and reusable (Schmidt, Thiery, and Trognitz, 2022). The *5-star data model* (Hasnain and Rebholz-Schuhmann, 2018), developed by Berners-Lee, is often used to assess the quality of LOD. Projects that document ontologies and schemas and make them reusable can even achieve the status of *7-star data* (Hyvönen et al., 2014). These extended models promote the sustainability and interoperability of data and actively contribute to the continuous expansion of the LOD Cloud and knowledge graphs such as Wikidata or Wikibase instances. The LOD Cloud is a (virtual) globally networked ecosystem of open, structured data linked together using semantic web technologies and made accessible via standardised formats such as RDF and SPARQL. Applied examples of LOD in the cultural heritage domain can be seen in (Isaksen, 2011; Schmidt, Thiery, and Trognitz, 2022; Thiery, Schenk, and Thiery, 2025; Thiery, 2013).

This project utilises the terminology applied in the archaeological conservation of the Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie (LEIZA) to illustrate the process and demonstrate the potential for developing semantically networked, machine-readable specialised thesauri.

Material & Data

The basis for our vocabulary development was indexing existing specialised terms from previous LEIZA conservation documentation. These "*worksheets*" (German: *Werkblätter*) constitute an archive of analogue and digital documentation that extends far back into LEIZA's (and former RGZMs) history of conservation. They consist of digitised handwritten index cards and digital reports as database entries, supplemented by attached digital documents in different formats. The LEIZA conservators themselves represent a second important source. In discussions with colleagues who describe particular objects or techniques daily and use the terminology in practice, further terms are identified. This source also records in-house jargon and terminological imprecision, which are "*oral terms*" and can be linked within the thesaurus to the correct scientific terminology in a professional context. Furthermore, previous considerations regarding terminologies at LEIZA offer valuable resources, including word lists, first tabular structuring drafts, discussion protocols, and notes.

Methodology

The central goal of our approach is to combine human understanding, semantic modelling techniques and natural language processing technologies to generate new knowledge. This tree-folded process inverts the human-in-the-loop principle (Yeruva et al., 2020) to our new so-called "semantics/algorithms-in-the-loop" approach:

1. A scientist collects, arranges, and validates subject-specific terms from existing sources in tabular form.
2. A semantic modeller transforms this data using RDF according to the Simple Knowledge Organisation System (SKOS) scheme (Miles and Bechhofer, 2009), performs data enrichment, and implements vagueness and uncertainty.
3. Algorithms and Machine Learning (ML) from the procedural and ML Era (McCreary, 2019) process text data from the domain in question to extract quantitative data automatically by using Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies and semantic reasoning.

This new approach leads to the Knowledge Graph Era, in which ML reads data, combines it with existing knowledge, and produces new knowledge for evaluation and integration by human specialists (McCreary, 2019).

Realisation

Based on the mentioned methodology, material and data, machine learning and NLP technology were applied and interactive web-based applications, such as FAIRification tools and Wikibase, were implemented. The following subsections provide illustrative examples of these implementations.

NLP Approaches

LEIZA's database incorporates approximately 57,000 conservation procedures, of which half are complemented by text descriptions in summary database fields or attached documents. Given the limitations on human time and the potential value of insights gained from large unstructured text data in our domain, we employed natural language processing (Brandsen, 2022: 22) techniques to search for relevant terms. The utilisation of these techniques has the potential to identify additional specialised terms for the description of conservation measures and provide a quantitative framework for their development. A reasonable basis for exploring the corpus is determining word frequencies, as relevant terms will appear more frequently in these domain documents.

The initial step of the project, which proved to be the most time-consuming part of the overall process, was data preparation and cleaning. To convert files from different formats, such as *ODT* and *DOC*, to *DOCX*, we used LibreOffice command-line functions (The Document Foundation, 2024), which allowed us to apply the same processing pipelines to all files. A significant number of PDF documents lacked embedded text, requiring optical character recognition. Given the additional challenge of handwriting detection, our initial focus was on printed text. To generate clean data, we utilised spaCy Layout, which integrates layout recognition with OCR (Montani and Aniol, [2024])

2025). This allowed us to annotate text from tables, footnotes, captions, and headers and process them differently. Consequently, we could remove element-related noise, such as numbers and special characters.

The following step involved segmenting strings of characters in sentences and words. The resulting sentences were additionally classified as formal sentences or just sets of words, determining whether they contain a subject and a predicate, consist of more than two words, and end with typical punctuation marks using *spaCy* (Honnibal et al., 2020). Thus, the sentence subset of the data can be used for techniques expecting rich semantic information.

To normalise the form in which the extracted words appear, they require conversion to their base form through lemmatisation (e.g., verbs are converted to their infinitives) and lowercasing for uppercase words at the beginning of sentences. Finally, excluding stop words that occur most frequently in any given text is necessary and does not contribute information about the domain.

The resulting word frequencies (Figure 1; Table 1) represent the domain vocabulary, with leading tokens such as "object," "water," "weight," "paraloid" (a polymer that conservation scientists commonly use), "fragment," or "form" (LEIZA and former RGZM are known for creating copies, which involves forms). Due to the substantial number of terms — exceeding 38,000 with counts up to over 7000¹ — it is impractical for the knowledge engineer to comprehensively integrate all of them by hand. However, terms with a high count can be prioritised and evaluated so no important terms are forgotten.

An essential component of thesauri is structuring hierarchical, equivalent and associative relationships between terms. For this reason, it was helpful to identify groups of terms with relationships when analysing the texts. A straightforward approach also involving term frequencies is calculating the co-occurrences of terms. These are terms that frequently appear together in documents or sentences. According to the distributional hypothesis, this joint appearance can be interpreted as a semantic connection (Firth, 1957). The application of this method to the semantically rich subset of the data has produced encouraging results, as evidenced by Figure 2, which presents a word cloud illustrating the co-occurrences of adhesive, prominently featuring words like *araldite* (an epoxy resin used for gluing) and *shard* (Table 2). A semantic connection is also evident between the term reproduction and its companions, namely *replica*, *form*, *silicone*, and *plastiline*, as these words describe the process of creating copies of objects. (Figure 3; Table 3).

Future research will employ more sophisticated and accurate techniques on the sentence subset of the data, beginning with static word embeddings, which generate a vector space of terms in which similarity can be calculated by distance measures (Mikolov et al., 2013; Pennington, Socher, and Manning, 2014). Creating topics — recurrent sets of terms — using latent Dirichlet allocation (Blei, Ng, and Jordan, 2003) might allow further exploratory insights into vocabulary relations. Given the potential of transformer language models based on deep neural networks and trained for general

¹ Terms that occur only once have been deleted because these hapax legomena are not relevant to our research and often contain noise like OCR errors.

language understanding, their application to our data could surpass these approaches (Grootendorst, 2022).

FAIRification Tool as Web Application

Organising vocabulary terms into tables has been shown to present novel challenges for knowledge engineers. As vocabulary density increases, the hierarchical structure in which the terms are organised within the tabular data becomes increasingly challenging to maintain, as illustrated by an extract from the table of the archaeological conservation thesaurus (Figure 4). Errors in data entry, such as the inadvertent duplication of a unique identifier, are inevitable for human operators. These challenges are addressed by our *FAIRification tool*, a web application designed to support knowledge engineers in their complex tasks and maintain coherence.

This tool enables uploading diverse table formats from local sources or retrieving online tables, such as shared spreadsheets. Upon reading the data, the application verifies against our SKOS-related model schema. Identifiers must be unique, and the concept hierarchy is subject to specific criteria. For instance, circular descent or terms without a "*parent*" (broader term assignment) is not permitted except for the terms at the highest hierarchical level. In the event of a detected problem, the concepts violating the established rules are displayed on the screen, along with an explanation of the error. This process eliminates the need for manual verification of each individual data entry.

Various visualisation options, such as trees, sunbursts, or icicles, are available through the d3.js library (Mempel-Länger, 2024c). These allow the current hierarchy to be monitored differently. Figure 5 demonstrates this with a collapsible tree visualisation of the physical condition branch of archaeological objects. Selecting the label of a concept in the visualisation initiates the opening of a new window, which contains comprehensive information, including synonyms, descriptions of the term's meaning and their source. For tables retrieved online, the ability to write and read comments on a concept and a navigable comment history permits asynchronous collaborative work on the vocabulary.

Finally, the table can be exported as a file written in the RDF Turtle dialect. It is a suitable format for FAIR thesaurus data (Figure 6), with an example of the concept of ceramic and its description and mappings in the Turtle dialect. The comments are also expressed in RDF, using the Web Annotation Ontology to relate them to the concepts discussed. A Solid Pod serves as a minimal storage space for them.

The decision to use simple table structures to initiate the vocabulary development/conversion process is based on the fact that internal terminologies in many GLAM institutions are in the form of tabular data. These documents represent a valuable knowledge asset in the field of cultural heritage. Our tool offers a lightweight approach, even for smaller institutions, to convert them into linked, open vocabulary data without dealing with a sophisticated terminology editor. Converted data can be effortlessly integrated into a SkoHub repository (Mempel-Länger, 2024b) by generating a GitHub page (Mempel-Länger, 2024a) or in other central vocabulary servers.

Wikibase modelling and impact on online repositories

To implement the FAIR principles using LOD technologies and formalisms, a *Wikibase* (Vrandečić, 2013; Rossenova, Duchesne, and Blümel, 2022) instance in the *wikibase.cloud*² is used, supported by an extended SKOS scheme. This enables interconnected objects, conservation processes and sources inside the LOD cloud. As a prototypical modelling structure, the items³ *SKOS Plus Class* (Q1), *Concept* and *Structural Concept* (Q2/Q3), *Concept Scheme* (Q4), and *Repository* (Q5) with its instances such as *Wikidata* (Q9), *Getty AAT* (Q11) or *CAMEO* (Q13) are used (Thiery, Fella, and Mempel-Länger, 2024a). These are combined with properties⁴ for statements, qualifiers and references like *notation/identifier* (P4), *identifier label* (P21), *description* (P24), the SKOS semantic relations *broader* (P7), *narrower* (P8), and *related* (P9), the extended SKOS properties *has source* (P27), *describing image* (P26), *resource example* (P29), as well as semantic alignments (SKOS mapping) *aligned with* (P17) with a value URI and the qualifiers *alignment type* (P18) and *alignment repository* (P19), cf. (Thiery, Fella, and Mempel-Länger, 2024b). The transformation from the previously mentioned CSV file as a basis is applied via a semi-automatic Research Software Engineering workflow using Python⁵ to create QuickStatements⁶ (Diefenbach et al., 2021) for the Wikibase Import.

A real-world illustration example drawn from the conservation thesaurus is the modelling of gold alloy (Q18) and silver alloy (Q19), as well as electrum (Q20), an alloy of gold and silver. *Electrum has source* (P27), i.e., (Wolters, 1989), is *aligned with* (P17), i.e., *Wikidata* (Q239481, skos:closeMatch), *CAMEO* (Electrum, skos:closeMatch), and *Getty AAT* (300010965, skos:closeMatch), and has *describing images* (P26) such as *electrum coins*⁷ as (P28) *Object Example* (Q22) from the IKMK collection (Figure 7). However, the added value only becomes visible when linked to domain-specific databases such as KUR⁸ or NAVISone⁹. KUR lists several *conservation methods* (Q25) for archaeological wood, such as *consolidation* (Q27) or *impregnation* (Q28), as well as *materials* (Q26), such as *Polyethylene glycol (PEG)* (Q29) or the melamine resin *Kauramin 800* (Q30) for *wet-wood* (de: archäologisches Holz) (Q31). For example, Q29 and Q30 were used in test series¹⁰ *V08_005* (Figure 8) and *V08_002* (Thiery, Homburg, et al., 2024), which will be transformed into LOD and will be part of the *NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph (N4O KG)*. The NAVISone wrecks mention several conservation methods and materials, such as PEG (Q29) in Haithabu 1¹¹ or melamine formaldehyde (Q32)

² cf. <https://www.wikibase.cloud/>

³ Prefix/Concept IRI: <[https://n4o-ta4-dev.wikibase.cloud/entity/Q\\$](https://n4o-ta4-dev.wikibase.cloud/entity/Q$)>

⁴ Prefix/Concept IRI: <[https://n4o-ta4-dev.wikibase.cloud/entity/P\\$](https://n4o-ta4-dev.wikibase.cloud/entity/P$)>

⁵ cf. <https://github.com/n4o-rse/ta4-conservation-wikibase-feedingqs/>

⁶ cf. <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Help:QuickStatements/en-gb>

⁷ i.e. <https://ikmk.smb.museum/object?id=18200106> and <https://ikmk.smb.museum/object?id=18202882>

⁸ <https://www1.rgzm.de/kur/>; KUR - Online database for the professional procedure for the mass supply of archaeological iron and moist wood finds.

⁹ <https://www2.leiza.de/navis/>: especially the former NAVIS I shipwreck database.

¹⁰ <https://t1p.de/gaywr>

¹¹ <https://www2.leiza.de/navis/object.html?id=100008>

in Mainz 5¹² (Figure 9), which will contribute to the NAVISone LOD¹³ within *archaeology.link* (Thiery and Mees, 2024) and the N4O KG.

Discussion & Outlook

This paper uses a practical example to show how a structured, human- and machine-actionable and -understandable thesaurus can be developed from unstructured terms to describe comprehensive conservation processes. The primary objective of this study is to examine the potential for synergistic collaboration between specialised scientists and technical experts and identify the challenges and obstacles encountered during the development process. Moreover, it sets the stage for future innovations in documenting and sharing archaeological conservation practices. It also enables the integration of thesauri and research data into the *NFDI ecosystem*, such as *DANTE* (as terminology hub), *cocoda* (as terminology mapping tool), the *N4O Knowledge Graph* and the *Base4NFDI* services *TS4NFDI* and *KGI4NFDI*.

As future conservation data is systematically integrated and linked with historical records, a globally accessible knowledge graph will emerge. This structure will enable the consistent referencing and exchange of identical elements across linguistic and regional boundaries. It is essential to highlight that conservation and restoration are inherently interdisciplinary fields. Structured semantics enables digital collaboration with cultural collections and the natural and life sciences. This aligns with the approach pursued within the *NFDI ecosystem*, underscoring its broader scientific value. By embedding conservation data within this interconnected ecosystem, restoration records will no longer exist in isolation. Still, they will instead form critical links to adjacent research domains, fostering enhanced interdisciplinary exchange and knowledge dissemination.

In the future, dealing with vagueness and uncertainties during the semantic alignment (Thiery and Mees, 2023), the technical possibilities (Unold, Thiery, and Mees, 2019; Tolle and Wigg-Wolf, 2015; Thiery et al., 2021; 2022; Thiery, Schenk, et al., 2024; Thiery, Schenk, and Thiery, 2025), issues and challenges (Weigel, 2024) as well as extend the “*predicate canon*” to describe vague, uncertain or ambiguous vocabulary terms (Nation, 2017; Thiery and Engel, 2016; Piotrowski et al., 2014) is a common topic that has to be addressed within the modelling community, also within the *NFDI4Objects ecosystem* (Thiery, Mees, and Arera-Rütenik, 2021; Thiery et al., 2021). The relationships in the resulting knowledge graph can also serve as a basis for further technological processing. Documents and database fields with unstructured text from the domain can be converted into structured knowledge using entity recognition, entity ambiguity and relation recognition techniques.

¹² <https://www2.leiza.de/navis/object.html?id=100030>

¹³ <https://archaeolink-lod.github.io/navisone/>

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to take this opportunity to thank the LEIZA conservators for providing the terminology data, conservation reports, and comprehensive preparatory work, as well as for the constructive exchange on structuring the thesaurus. The linguistic smoothing of the formulations was achieved by utilising the AI software *claude.ai*, *Grammarly* and *ChatGPT*, while the translation into English was facilitated by the AI-supported software *DeepL*. This project was funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) - Project number 501836407 (NFDI4Objects) and the Ministry of Science and Health of the State of Rhineland-Palatinate with the Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie (LEIZA) as a partner institution.

Author Contributions

The author's contributions follow the CRediT system. The abbreviations are Lasse Mempel-Länger (LML), Kristina Fella (KT), and Florian Thiery (FT).

Conceptualization: LML; KF; FTM; **Data curation:** KF; **Formal Analysis:** LML; KF; FT; **Investigation:** LML; KF; **Methodology:** LML; KF; FT; **Project Administration:** LML; KF; FT; **Resources:** LML; KF; FT; **Software:** LML; FT; **Validation:** LML; KF; **Visualization:** LML; KF; FT; **Writing – original draft:** LML; KF; FT; **Writing – review & editing:** N.N.

Conflicts of Interest disclosure

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Beck, L. S. (2013), 'DIGITAL DOCUMENTATION IN THE CONSERVATION OF CULTURAL HERITAGE: FINDING THE PRACTICAL IN BEST PRACTICE', *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, XL-5-W2, 85–90. doi: [10.5194/isprsarchives-XL-5-W2-85-2013](https://doi.org/10.5194/isprsarchives-XL-5-W2-85-2013).
- Berners-Lee, T. (2006), 'Linked Data'. Available at: <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html> (Accessed 28 January 2025).
- Bibby, D., K.-C. Bruhn, A. Busch, F. Dührkohp, and et al. (2023), 'NFDI4Objects - Proposal', *NFDI4Objects Zenodo Community*. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.10409227](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10409227).
- Blei, D. M., A. Y. Ng, and M. I. Jordan (2003), 'Latent dirichlet allocation', *J. Mach. Learn. Res.*, 3, 993–1022.
- Brandsen, A. (2022), 'Digging in documents: using text mining to access the hidden knowledge in Dutch archaeological excavation reports' (Leiden University). Available at: <https://hdl.handle.net/1887/3274287> (Accessed 30 January 2025).
- Diefenbach, D., M. D. Wilde, M. D. Wilde, and S. Alipio (2021), 'Wikibase as an Infrastructure for Knowledge Graphs: The EU Knowledge Graph', in *The Semantic Web – ISWC 2021: 20th International Semantic Web Conference, ISWC 2021, Virtual Event, October 24–28, 2021, Proceedings*, pp. 631–47. doi: [10.1007/978-3-030-88361-4_37](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-88361-4_37).
- Fella, K., L. Mempel-Länger, and N. Witt (2024), 'NFDI4Objects - Community Cluster "Konservierung und Restaurierung/ Conservation Science"'. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.11370865](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11370865).
- Firth, J. R. (1957), 'A synopsis of linguistic theory 1930-1955', in *Studies in Linguistic Analysis* (Oxford: Blackwell), pp. 1–32.

- Grootendorst, M. (2022), 'BERTopic: Neural topic modeling with a class-based TF-IDF procedure'. doi: [10.48550/ARXIV.2203.05794](https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2203.05794).
- Harpring, P. (2010), *Introduction to Controlled Vocabularies: Terminology for Art, Architecture, and Other Cultural Works*, 1st ed (Los Angeles, Calif: Getty Research Institute).
- Hasnain, A., and D. Rebolz-Schuhmann (2018), 'Assessing FAIR Data Principles Against the 5-Star Open Data Principles', in A. Gangemi, A. L. Gentile, A. G. Nuzzolese, S. Rudolph, M. Maleshkova, H. Paulheim, et al. (eds), *The Semantic Web: ESWC 2018 Satellite Events* (Cham: Springer International Publishing), pp. 469–77. doi: [10.1007/978-3-319-98192-5_60](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-98192-5_60).
- Himmelmann, U., R. Schwab, S. Metz, T. Krenscher, F. Thiery, J. Lefeldt, et al. (2024), 'Forschungsdatenmanagement im Bereich Denkmalpflege, Archäologie und Restaurierung'. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.10978098](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10978098).
- Honnibal, M., I. Montani, S. Van Landeghem, and A. Boyd (2020), 'spaCy: Industrial-strength Natural Language Processing in Python' (Berlin, Germany: explosion).
- Hyvönen, E., J. Tuominen, M. Alonen, and E. Mäkelä (2014), 'Linked Data Finland: A 7-star Model and Platform for Publishing and Re-using Linked Datasets', in V. Presutti, E. Blomqvist, R. Troncy, H. Sack, I. Papadakis, and A. Tordai (eds), *The Semantic Web: ESWC 2014 Satellite Events* (Cham: Springer International Publishing), pp. 226–30. doi: [10.1007/978-3-319-11955-7_24](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-11955-7_24).
- Isaksen, L. (2011), 'Archaeology and the Semantic Web' (Thesis (Doctoral), University of Southampton, School of Electronics and Computer Science). Available at: <https://eprints.soton.ac.uk/id/eprint/206421> (Accessed: 12 May 2025).
- McCreary, D. (2019), 'Knowledge Graphs: The Third Era of Computing', *Medium*. Available at: <https://dmccreary.medium.com/knowledge-graphs-the-third-era-of-computing-a8106f343450> (Accessed: 29 July 2024).
- Mempel-Länger, L. (2024a), 'LasseMempel/RestSkos-pages', *GitHub*, LasseMempel. Available at: <https://github.com/LasseMempel/terminologies> (Accessed: 29 July 2024).
- (2024b), 'LasseMempel/RestSkos-pages/skosifyCSV', *GitHub*, LasseMempel. Available at: <https://github.com/LasseMempel/RestSkos-pages/tree/main/skosifyCSV> (Accessed: 29 July 2024).
- (2024c), 'LasseMempel/ta4-conservation-dev', *GitHub*, LasseMempel. Available at: <https://github.com/LasseMempel/ta4-conservation-dev> (Accessed: 29 July 2024).
- Mikolov, T., K. Chen, G. Corrado, and J. Dean (2013), 'Efficient Estimation of Word Representations in Vector Space' (arXiv). doi: [10.48550/ARXIV.1301.3781](https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.1301.3781).
- Miles, A., and S. Bechhofer (2009), 'SKOS Simple Knowledge Organization System Reference'. Available at: <https://www.w3.org/TR/2009/REC-skos-reference-20090818/> (Accessed 21 June 2024).
- Montani, I., and M. Aniol ((2024) 2025), 'spaCy Layout' (Berlin, Germany: Explosion). Available at: <https://github.com/explosion/spacy-layout> (Accessed 30 January 2025).
- Nation, Z. (2017), 'Perceptions of Probability and Numbers'. Available at: <https://github.com/zonation/perceptions> (Accessed 21 June 2024).
- Pennington, J., R. Socher, and C. Manning (2014), 'Glove: Global Vectors for Word Representation', *Proceedings of the 2014 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing (EMNLP)* (presented at the Proceedings of the 2014 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing (EMNLP), Doha, Qatar: Association for Computational Linguistics), pp. 1532–43. doi: [10.3115/v1/D14-1162](https://doi.org/10.3115/v1/D14-1162).
- Piotrowski, M., G. Colavizza, F. Thiery, and K.-C. Bruhn (2014), 'The Labeling System: A New Approach to Overcome the Vocabulary Bottleneck', *DH-CASE II: Collaborative Annotations on Shared Environments: Metadata, Tools and Techniques in the Digital Humanities - DH-CASE '14* (presented at the DH-CASE II: Collaborative Annotations, Fort Collins, CA, USA: ACM Press), pp. 1–6. doi: [10.1145/2657480.2657482](https://doi.org/10.1145/2657480.2657482).
- Rossenova, L., P. Duchesne, and I. Blümel (2022), 'Wikidata and Wikibase as complementary research data management services for cultural heritage data', *Proceedings of the 3rd Wikidata Workshop 2022 Co-Located with the 21st*

International Semantic Web Conference (ISWC2022). Available at: <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3262/paper15.pdf> (Accessed 28 January 2025).

Schmidt, S. C., F. Thiery, and M. Trognitz (2022), 'Practices of Linked Open Data in Archaeology and Their Realisation in Wikidata', *Digital*, 2:3, 333–64. doi: [10.3390/digital2030019](https://doi.org/10.3390/digital2030019).

Schreiber, G., and Y. Raimond (2014), 'RDF 1.1 Primer'. Available at: <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf11-primer/> (Accessed 28 January 2025).

The Document Foundation (2024), 'LibreOffice' (Berlin, Germany: The Document Foundation).

Thiery, F. (2013), 'Semantic Web und Linked Data: Generierung von Interoperabilität in archäologischen Fachdaten am Beispiel römischer Töpferstempel', *Squirrel Papers*, 4:1, #3. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.774861](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.774861).

Thiery, F., and T. Engel (2016), 'The Labeling System: The Labelling System: A Bottom-up Approach for Enriched Vocabularies in the Humanities', in S. Campana, R. Scopigno, G. Carpentiero, and M. Cirillo (eds), *CAA2015. Keep the Revolution Going. Proceedings of the 43rd Annual Conference on Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology*. (Oxford: Archaeopress), pp. 259–68.

Thiery, F., K. Fella, and L. Mempel-Länger (2024a), 'N4o-ta4-dev.wikibase.cloud | items.csv', *GitHub*, leiza-scit. Available at: <https://github.com/leiza-scit/n4o-ta4-dev.wikibase.cloud/blob/main/items.csv> (Accessed: 29 July 2024).

——— (2024b), 'N4o-ta4-dev.wikibase.cloud | properties.csv', *GitHub*, leiza-scit. Available at: <https://github.com/leiza-scit/n4o-ta4-dev.wikibase.cloud/blob/main/properties.csv> (Accessed: 29 July 2024).

Thiery, F., K. Fella, L. Mempel-Länger, and A. Puhl (2025), 'Digitale Services in der Archäologie: Aktuelle Entwicklungen und Angebote aus den NFDI4Objects Task Areas Collecting und Protecting', *Archäologische Informationen*, 47:NWDVA 2024 Bochum: Digitale Archäologie, Early View. Available at: https://dqf.de/fileadmin/AI/archinf-ev_thiery-et-al.pdf (Accessed: 20 January 2025).

Thiery, F., T. Homburg, A.-K. Distel, and P. Thiery (2024), '3D und FDM: Beispiele für semantische 3D-Annotation und -Modellierung im Datenqualifizierungsprozess in Konsortien der Nationalen Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI)', in T. Luhmann and T. Sieberth (eds), *Photogrammetrie – Laserscanning – Optische 3D-Messtechnik. Beiträge Der Oldenburger 3D-Tage Und Des BIMtages 2024*. (Berlin: Wichmann Verlag), pp. 84–93. Available at: <https://www.vde-verlag.de/buecher/537750/photogrammetrie-laserscanning-optische-3d-messtechnik.html> (Accessed: 20 January 2025).

Thiery, F., and A. Mees (2023), 'Taming Ambiguity - Dealing with doubts in archaeological datasets using LOD', *CAA 2018: Human History and Digital Future*. doi: [10.15496/PUBLIKATION-87762](https://doi.org/10.15496/PUBLIKATION-87762).

Thiery, F., A. Mees, and T. Arera-Rütenik (2021), 'TRAIL 4.2: Implementing mapping processes for vocabularies related to site and object protection'. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.5849841](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5849841).

Thiery, F., A. Mees, K. Tolle, and D. Wigg-Wolf (2021), 'TRAIL 2.2: Evaluation of fuzziness and wobbliness in numismatics and ceramology', *NFDI4Objects TRAILS*, 2021, No. 2.2. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.5654897](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654897).

Thiery, F., and A. W. Mees (2024), 'Sharing Linked Open Data with domain-specific data-driven community hubs – archaeology.link in NFDI4Objects', *Archeologia e Calcolatori*, 35:2, 63–74. doi: [10.19282/ac.35.2.2024.08](https://doi.org/10.19282/ac.35.2.2024.08).

Thiery, F., A. W. Mees, K. Tolle, and D. G. Wigg-Wolf (2022), 'How to handle vagueness and uncertainty in graph-based LOD knowledge modelling? Dealing with archaeological numismatic and ceramological real world data.', *Squirrel Papers*, 4:1, No. 2. doi: [10.5281/ZENODO.7184523](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7184523).

Thiery, F., A. W. Mees, B. Weisser, F. F. Schäfer, S. Baars, S. Nolte, et al. (2023), 'Object-Related Research Data Workflows Within NFDI4Objects and Beyond', *Proceedings of the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure*, 1. doi: [10.52825/cordi.v1i.326](https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.326).

Thiery, F., F. Schenk, S. Baars, K. Tolle, and P. Thiery (2024), 'Modellierung von Fuzzyness / Wobbliness in Geodaten', *Tagungsband FOSSGIS-Konferenz 2024*, 2024, 64–73. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.10571859](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10571859).

Thiery, F., F. Schenk, and P. Thiery (2025), 'Das Research Squirrel Engineers Network: FAIRification Tools und LOD-

Projekte aus der Archäoinformatik und den Geowissenschaften', *Archäologische Informationen*, 47:NWDVA 2024 Bochum: Digitale Archäologie, Early View.

Tolle, K., and D. Wigg-Wolf (2015), 'Uncertainty Handling for Ancient Coinage', in F. Giligny, F. Djindjian, L. Costa, P. Moscati, and S. Robert (eds), *CAA2014. 21st Century Archaeology. Concepts, Methods and Tools. Proceedings of the 42nd Annual Conference on Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology*. (Oxford: Archaeopress), pp. 171–78.

Unold, M., F. Thiery, and A. Mees (2019), 'Academic Meta Tool. Ein Web-Tool zur Modellierung von Vagheit', *ZfdG - Zeitschrift Für Digitale Geisteswissenschaften*, Die Modellierung des Zweifels – Schlüsselideen und-konzepte zur graphbasierten Modellierung von Unsicherheiten.:Sonderband 4. doi: [10.17175/SB004_004](https://doi.org/10.17175/SB004_004).

Vrandečić, D. (2013), 'The Rise of Wikidata', *IEEE Intelligent Systems*, 28:4, 90–95. doi: [10.1109/MIS.2013.119](https://doi.org/10.1109/MIS.2013.119).

Weigel, J. (2024), 'Uncertainty Reasoner for RDF Graphs based on Numismatic Use Cases' (Master Thesis, Johann Wolfgang Goethe-Universität Frankfurt am Mainz). Available at: <https://github.com/jensw99/uncertainty-reasoner/blob/main/master-thesis.pdf> (Accessed: 20 January 2025).

Wilkinson, M. D., M. Dumontier, I. J. Aalbersberg, G. Appleton, and et al. (2016), 'The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship', *Scientific Data*, 3, 160018. doi: [10.1038/sdata.2016.18](https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18).

Wolters, J. (1989), *Der Gold- Und Silberschmied. Band 1: Werkstoffe Und Materialien*. (Stuttgart: Rühle-Diebener-Verlag).

Yeruva, V. K., M. Chandrashekar, Y. Lee, J. Rydberg-Cox, V. Blanton, and N. A. Oyler (2020), 'Interpretation of Sentiment Analysis with Human-in-the-Loop', *2020 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (Big Data)*, pp. 3099–3108. doi: [10.1109/BigData50022.2020.9378221](https://doi.org/10.1109/BigData50022.2020.9378221).

List of Figures

No.	Caption	Width (8 or 17 cm)
Fig. 1	word cloud of the term frequencies in the corpus. © CC BY 4.0, Lasse Mempel-Länger.	8
Fig. 2	word cloud of the co-occurrences of glue. © CC BY 4.0, Lasse Mempel-Länger.	8
Fig. 3	word cloud of the co-occurrences of reproduction. © CC BY 4.0, Lasse Mempel-Länger.	8
Fig. 4	archaeological conservation thesaurus organised in a table. © CC BY 4.0, Lasse Mempel-Länger.	17
Fig. 5	visualisation of the thesaurus tree's object condition branch. © CC BY 4.0, Lasse Mempel-Länger.	8
Fig. 6	concept ceramic expressed in Turtle. © CC BY 4.0, Lasse Mempel-Länger.	8
Fig. 7	left: electrum (Q20) in the n4o-ta4-dev Wikibase; right: coin examples (Athen?, ID:18200106; Electron, ID:18202882; Karthago,	17

	ID:18223276) from IKMK, Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen, Berlin. © CC BY 4.0, Florian Thiery; Wikibase: CC BY; Coins: Public Domain.	
Fig. 8	left: Kauramin 800 (Q30) in the n4o-ta4-dev Wikibase; right: example V08_005 from the KUR project. © CC BY 4.0, Florian Thiery; Wikibase: CC BY; KUR: CC BY 4.0, RGZM/LEIZA.	17
Fig. 9	left: melamine formaldehyde (Q32) in the n4o-ta4-dev Wikibase; right: Mainz 5 ship in NAVISone and images from the excavation. © CC BY-SA 4.0, Florian Thiery; Wikibase: CC BY; NAVISone: CC BY 4.0, LEIZA; excavation images: CC BY-SA 4.0, RGZM and R. Wahl (1981/82); exhibition image: CC BY-SA 4.0, RGZM / V. Iserhardt (1998).	17

List of Tables

Please enter all the numbers and captions of tables in the table below.

No.	Caption
Tab. 1	Term frequencies of the LEIZA worksheet corpus.
Tab. 2	Co-occurrence frequencies of glue.
Tab. 3	Co-occurrence frequencies of reproduction.